

Frontiers of Laser-Based 3D Printing: A Perspective on Multi-Photon Lithography

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Lasers are instrumental in enabling precise processing and fostering the development of new technologies. Particularly, ultrafast lasers, due to their unique interaction with matter, can achieve not only exceptional spatial precision but also meticulously determine the degree of modification. A prime example of this is laser-based 3D printing through multi-photon lithography (MPL). This approach remarkably enables the printing of true 3D structures at the micro- and nanoscale, without the need for masks or cumbersome tools, simply by using computer-aided designs. Owing to these unique capabilities, MPL has emerged as a powerful manufacturing technique across various multidisciplinary fields. The ongoing growth in MPL's utilization has led to notable advancements in printing highly complex structures on different substrates, as well as improvements in resolution and throughput, and the development of novel photosensitive materials, which impressively facilitated MPL's expansion into broader fields over the last few years. In this perspective article, the aim is to highlight these advancements and recent trends in MPL. The current challenges of MPL will be explored, which need to be addressed to ensure its further integration into advanced Additive Manufacturing at the micro- and nanoscale. The future perspectives and opportunities of MPL as a laser-based 3D printing approach will also be discussed.

3D printing processes employing lasers can be initiated by linear one-photon absorption when the laser wavelength is within the absorption spectrum of the photosensitive material.^[2,3] Intriguingly, 3D printing can also be realized with materials transparent to a given laser wavelength, provided the laser's energy is precisely confined both spatially and temporally. This process was first described by Goeppert-Mayer in 1931.^[4] It involves, in its simplest form, the nonlinear quasi-simultaneous absorption of two photons. Here, the absorption of the first photon excites an electron to an intermediate state with a lifetime in the femtosecond (fs) regime, while the absorption of the second photon within this lifetime triggers the full excitation event.

In the late 1990s, the practical application of two-photon absorption was realized with the advent of ultrashort pulsed laser technology, capable of delivering enough photons in both time and space to fulfill this nonlinear absorption

process.^[5] Such an advancement led to a groundbreaking achievement in manufacturing known as two-photon polymerization (TPP or 2PP),^[6] or two-photon lithography (TPL or 2PL),^[7] allowing for the accurate processing of UV-sensitive resins with submicron resolution. Today, we understand that this process can be triggered not only by the absorption of two photons but also by multiple photons.^[8,9] Hence, in this perspective article, we refer to this process as multi-photon lithography (MPL) to provide a more accurate description of this laser-based 3D printing approach.

In practical terms, MPL operates on a principle that involves using tightly focused fs laser radiation in a photosensitive material, with the physics detailed in ref. [10]. As a result, a small building block, known as a voxel (volume pixel), is generated in an area where the laser intensity surpasses a certain threshold, with photoexcitation mechanisms detailed in ref. [11] (Figure 1A). Typically, the conditions for threshold excitation are only met within a confined region inside the focal volume of the laser beam.^[12] In this way, the voxel size can surpass the traditional diffraction limit, enabling MPL to print features with sub-diffraction resolution.^[13] Nevertheless, the size of a voxel can be effectively modulated towards higher values by simply adjusting the laser intensity (Figure 1A).^[14,15]

1. Introduction

Laser-based 3D printing of photosensitive materials represents a form of additive manufacturing (AM). This process involves stimulating the transition of molecules from their ground state to an excited state, thereby triggering a photochemical reaction that typically results in polymerization. The precision with which lasers interact with matter renders laser-based 3D printing a highly innovative and rapidly evolving technique that holds significant promise for the future, offering cost-effective and sustainable fabrication of high-resolution structures.^[1,2]

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Figure 1. MPL. A) Principle of MPL: A small building block (voxel) occurs when the laser intensity surpasses the polymerization threshold. The size of the voxel can be adjusted by modulating the laser intensity until the damage threshold, where the printed structure gets destroyed. 3D printing is achieved through the targeted assembly of individual voxels. Modulating the laser intensity can enable higher precision and speed. B) Trend in MPL research: The graph shows the increasing number of published papers and citations over the past two decades involving MPL. Data was compiled from the Web of Science using keywords such as "two-photon polymerization," "two-photon lithography," "multi-photon polymerization," and "multi-photon lithography." SEM images illustrate the evolution of structures printed using MPL. 2009: Spiral photonic crystal. Scale bar: 16 μm . Reproduced with permission.^[7] Copyright 2009 The Authors, published by Nature Publishing Group. 2017: Complex micro-lens system fabricated by MPL. Scale bar: 30 μm . Reproduced under terms of the CC-BY license.^[16] Copyright 2017 The Authors, published by The American Association for the Advancement of Science. 2023: Sail-boats printed by MPL and transferred to a complex surface. Scale bar: 20 μm . Reproduced under terms of the CC-BY license.^[17] Copyright 2023 The Authors, published by Wiley-VCH.

Combining tight focusing with precise guidance of the laser beam within the photosensitive material allows for the targeted assembly of individual voxels in both 2D and 3D configurations at arbitrary positions. This approach ultimately facilitates maskless 3D printing (Figure 1A), a process that simply involves using computer models sliced into layers, with each layer hatched to define the laser's exposure paths. Notably, MPL, due to its non-linear nature, stands out for its ability to create structures of any complexity, with no restrictions on shapes and geometries.

The unique combination of precision, flexibility, versatility, and high resolution achievable through a single technique clearly distinguishes MPL from conventional lithography methods^[18,19] and traditional laser-based 3D printing techniques,^[3] which typically rely on one-photon absorption.

Therefore, the use of MPL has continuously gained attractiveness over the past decade, particularly in multidisciplinary research fields. This upward trend is evident in the rising number of published papers and citations related to MPL (Figure 1B). The growth of MPL has been significantly boosted by the development of specifically designed photosensitive materials,^[20,21] as well as the commercialization of MPL printers.^[22]

Especially within the last five years, MPL has increasingly emerged as a cornerstone in the field of laser-based 3D printing, particularly in areas requiring micro-/nanostructures, where the challenges of miniaturization and complexity enhancement are prevalent. This emergence is notably significant in fields where the precision and versatility of MPL offer distinct advan-

tages in processing. Such fields include photonics,^[23] optics,^[24] metamaterials,^[25] biomimetics,^[26] and life science, encompassing microfluidics,^[27] lab-on-chip applications,^[28] biomedicine,^[29] among many others. Meanwhile, the increased interest in utilizing MPL, further driven by the growing trend in 3D printing across industry and science, has positively influenced the development of the technique, leading to significant general advancements and others in materials, resolution, and throughput.

In this perspective article, we aim to highlight the recent advancements and trends, along with their potential applications. We will further delve into the current challenges faced by MPL, offering our insights on how these challenges can be addressed to enhance MPL's effectiveness, thus ensuring its continuous growth. In light of these considerations, we will discuss the future perspectives and opportunities for MPL in advanced additive manufacturing (AM) at the micro- and nanoscale, aiming at exploring ways to foster MPL applicability across various research fields and in industry.

2. Recent Advancements and Trends in MPL

2.1. General Advancement

The traditional MPL process is typically conducted serially, either point-by-point or line-by-line, employing fs lasers that emit light in the near-infrared (NIR) or visible (VIS) spectrum. The central wavelengths are usually 780 nm for NIR and 515 nm for VIS, with

Figure 2. Advanced MPL-based 3D printing. A) MPL applicable across the spectrum from 500 to 1200 nm. Scale bar: 20 μm . Reproduced under terms of CC-BY license.^[36] Copyright 2023 The Authors, published by Informa UK Limited, trading as Taylor & Francis Group. B) MPL-based printing mesoscale butterfly structure by the synchronization of translation stages and galvo scanner. The printed butterfly structure exhibits high-resolution features. Reproduced under Optica Publishing Group Open Access Publishing Agreement.^[37] Copyright 2019 The Authors, published by Optica Publishing Group. C) Grayscale-based MPL enable high-resolution printing of micro-optics. Reproduced under Optica Publishing Group Open Access Publishing Agreement.^[38] Copyright 2023 The Authors, published by Optica Publishing Group. D) Micro-optics printed on a CMOS image sensor (left) and a detailed photograph of these micro-optics (right). Reproduced under terms of the CC-BY license.^[16] Copyright 2017 The Authors, published by The American Association for the Advancement of Science. E) Examples of 3D printed structures on an optical fiber via MPL: i) Micro-ring resonator, achieving a Q factor of 2×10^3 . Reproduced with permission.^[39] Copyright 2021 IEEE. ii) Force sensor comprised by a 3D micro-grasper. Reproduced with permission.^[40] Copyright 2018 Wiley-VCH. F) 3D printed electrodes on flexible substrates: A cropped photograph showing polyimide flex cable on a finger. Reproduced under terms of CC-BY license.^[41] Copyright 2023 The Authors, published by Nature Publishing Group. G) Photonic wire bonding for PIC applications: i) and ii) Fiber-to-chip interface connected via 3D-printed photonic wire bonds. Connection of tapered ends of SiP strip waveguides through 3D-printed photonic wire bonds. Reproduced under terms of CC-BY license.^[42] Copyright 2020 The Authors, published by Nature Publishing Group. iii) 3D-printed photonic wire bonds bridging an InP laser and SiP chip. Reproduced under Optica Publishing Group Open Access Publishing Agreement.^[43] Copyright 2018, The Authors, published by Optica Publishing Group. H) Facile handling of 3D microstructures printed through MPL: i) Human hair covered with 3D-printed microstructures. ii) A diver, fabricated via MPL, transferred onto a cantilever tip. Reproduced under terms under terms of CC-BY license.^[17] Copyright 2023 The Authors, published by Wiley-VCH.

a pulse width ranging from 100 to 300 fs and a pulse repetition rate spanning from 100 kHz to 82 MHz,^[22,30] although laser systems with shorter^[31–33] and longer pulse width^[34,35] and higher repetition in GHz regime rate can also be used.^[34]

In general, NIR sources are often preferred, as most materials used today exhibit great transparency to NIR light, resulting in minimal linear interaction with this wavelength. However, a novel study by Skliutas et al.^[36] has expanded the potential for next-generation fs laser sources for MPL, extending the spectral range from 500 to 1200 nm (Figure 2A). This study revealed that MPL is more complex than merely two-photon absorption, making ‘multi-photon’ absorption a more fitting term. Additionally, the authors revealed that complex photophysical mechanisms, such as avalanche ionization, can also be involved in MPL-based 3D printing, particularly with a higher degree of nonlinearity.

Regardless of the laser wavelengths or the photophysical mechanisms involved, initiating a photochemical reaction in photosensitive materials through nonlinear light-matter interac-

tions requires a minimum pulse peak intensity of about $\text{TW}\cdot\text{cm}^{-2}$.^[36,44] To achieve these intensities, microscope objectives with numerical apertures ranging from 0.2 to 1.4 are commonly used. Moreover, MPL printers are equipped with precise systems to deliver laser radiation to specific positions. These systems typically include galvanometric scanners combined with linear translation XYZ axis systems for fast printing processes, or piezoelectrical axis systems for high-resolution tasks.^[30] It is also possible to synchronize galvanometric scanners with linear axis systems to enable continuous printing without the need for stitching (Figure 2B).^[37]

Furthermore, shutters, whether mechanical or acousto-optical, are used to control material exposure. Acousto-optical modulators, in particular, allow for rapid adjustments in laser intensity during printing,^[45] enabling quick modulation of voxel size and facilitating precise control over resolution and refractive index at any position.^[46] Recently, this approach has been introduced as grayscale lithography,^[38,47,48] holding significant potential for

enhancing the quality of structures, especially those with curved surfaces (Figure 2C) and shortening production time. Grayscale-based MPL thus broadens the scope of already existing adaptive manufacturing strategies, which are comprehensively demonstrated by Zhou et al.^[30] and Gonzalez-Hernandez et al.^[24] Particularly, the fabrication of micro-optical elements, such as gradient refractive index (GRIN) elements,^[49] micro-lenses,^[50] diffractive optical elements,^[51,52] and waveguides,^[53] is poised to greatly benefit from these advancements in MPL.

An additional trend in MPL printing is the fabrication of structures on diverse substrates. Initially focused on transparent substrates, MPL-based 3D printing has now successfully expanded to include non-transparent, technologically significant substrates. Noteworthy examples include fabricating micro-optics on CMOS image sensors^[16] (Figure 2D) and electromagnetic metamaterials for terahertz (THz) applications on silicon substrates.^[54]

The versatility and great adaptability of MPL further allows for 3D printing on surfaces that are hard to access, such as optical fibers, presenting significant opportunities for developing novel sensing or optical applications. This includes, for instance, micro-ring resonators (Figure 2E, i)^[39] and micro-graspers (Figure 2E, ii),^[40,55] while the full potential of MPL in 3D printing on optical fibers is extensively explored in the review by Xiong et al.^[56] Other examples in this context include the successful fabrication of 3D electrodes on flexible substrates for neural recording in small animals (Figure 2F),^[41] and the realization of photonic wire bonds to efficiently connect photonic integrated circuits (PICs) (Figure 2G).^[42,43]

Moreover, a recent substantial contribution by den Hoed et al.^[17] has further expanded MPL's capabilities. They introduced a method for the facile handling of microstructures printed via MPL using nanomembranes. This innovative technique greatly simplifies the transfer of microstructures to various substrates (Figure 2H), including human hairs, cantilevers, and wires, potentially marking a considerable advancement in MPL technology and its applications, such as the generation of flexible electromagnetic metamaterials.^[57]

2.2. Advancements in Photosensitive Materials

In general, any materials sensitive to light can be processed through MPL, provided they meet the conditions for multi-photon absorption. This category includes, for instance, metal salts,^[58,59] natural proteins,^[60] biomaterials^[61] or positive photoresists.^[62] Nevertheless, negative photoresists are still the most commonly used materials in MPL. The main components of a negative photoresist are a monomer-oligomer mixture and a photoinitiator that helps initialize the effective cross-linking of the material, primarily achieved through radical and occasionally cationic polymerization.^[63]

In this context, various organic photoresists have been successfully utilized in MPL. These include hydrogels, and epoxies, as well as acrylates, which include the *IP-series* from Nanoscribe.^[20] A comprehensive overview of MPL materials is provided in recent reviews by Wang et al.^[23] and O'Halloran et al.^[63]

Nevertheless, hybrid photoresists, which merge organic and inorganic components, are among the most frequently used materials in MPL. Notably, silica-based OrmoComp[®], known for

its glass-like characteristics,^[47,64] and SZ2080, recognized for its ultra-low shrinkage,^[21,65,66] are prominent commercially available options. The growing interest in hybrid photoresists is due to their potential for flexibly tailoring properties such as physical, biological, thermal, mechanical, electrical, electrochemical, optical, and photonic ones.^[67] This versatility is achieved by carefully selecting appropriate organic and inorganic constituents, and sometimes, by adding additives such as carbon nanotubes,^[68] iron nanoparticles,^[69] or quantum dots.^[70]

Specifically, post-processing techniques have recently enhanced the utility of hybrid photoresists. Atomic layer deposition, for instance, can be employed to enhance the transparency of printed structures, an approach that is particularly relevant for micro-optics.^[71] Moreover, if the inorganic component of the photoresist contains sufficient metal-binding moieties, printed micro- or nanostructures can be selectively metalized through silver electroless plating, proving to be highly effective in the production of electromagnetic metamaterials (Figure 3A).^[66,72] Another growing trend in post-processing is the heat treatment of micro- and nanostructures, known as pyrolysis or calcination.^[73] Aimed at removing the organic component, this process enables the creation of purely inorganic materials at the micro- and nano-scale, such as metals or metal oxides (Figure 3B).^[74,75] Notably, fully dense titanium dioxide (TiO₂) structures with a refractive index of up to 2.3 could be achieved in this way,^[76] surpassing the refractive index attainable by integrating TiO₂ nanoparticles into a photoresist.^[77] Moreover, post-heat treatment can release shrinkage-induced tensions, eliminate the photoinitiator and enhance cross-linking.^[78]

Furthermore, recent studies have increasingly focused on enhancing the effectiveness of various photosensitive materials in MPL printing and related applications by using novel photoinitiators. For instance, Ladika et al.^[89] demonstrated the impact of triphenylamine-based aldehydes as photoinitiators on the fabrication process, suggesting that the use of these photoinitiators can lead to improved speed and precision in controlling the voxel size due. Furthermore, Liu et al.^[90] introduced a new photoresist that incorporates a sensitive photoinitiator with ZrO₂ hybrid nanoparticles, enabling rapid processing of microstructures at high scanning speeds using a polygon scanner. Typically, improvements in voxel size control and speed are based on the enhanced two-photon absorption cross-sections of the photoinitiators, which can positively affect both sensitivity and the fabrication process window.^[91] Additionally, the use of Sudan Black B (SBB) as photoinitiator has demonstrated significant effectiveness in addressing the challenge of mitigating undesired fluorescence, a common issue with MPL photoresists due to the optical properties of photoinitiators. This optimization achieved by leveraging SBB's ability to absorb light in the visible ranges is highly beneficial for tissue engineering, especially when characterizing scaffolds via confocal microscopy.^[19,92] Further recent studies and a comprehensive overview of photoinitiators for natural and synthetic polymers suitable for MPL processing are provided by Kiefer et al.^[93] Wloka et al.,^[94] and Grant et al.^[95]

In parallel, significant advancements in the development of novel photosensitive materials for MPL have been highlighted in recent works. While Kotz et al.^[79] investigated the efficient chemical cross-linking of a Glassomer silica nanocomposite material. In this context, they achieved transparent fused silica glass

Figure 3. Advanced materials and resolution in MPL-based 3D printing. A) 3D electromagnetic metamaterial structure printed by MPL, followed by silver electroless plating post-processing. Reproduced under terms of CC-BY license.^[66] Copyright 2020 The Authors, published by Nature Publishing Group. B) Nickel truss lattice structure with micro- and nanoscale features, fabricated using hybrid photoresists and pyrolysis post-processing. Scale bars: 2 μm . (left), 500 nm (right). Reproduced under terms of CC-BY license.^[74] Copyright 2018 The Authors, published by Nature Publishing Group. C) Glass microrook printed by MPL. Scale bars: 200 μm . Reproduced under terms of CC-BY license.^[79] Copyright 2021 The Authors, published by Wiley-VCH. D) MPL-based 3D printing of hybrid inorganic inks (top), inorganic multimaterials (center), and various ink photographs (bottom). Scale bars: 1 μm (top, pyramidal structure), 10 μm (top, "Loong" pattern), 5 μm (center, N-shaped pin pattern). Reproduced with permission.^[80] Copyright 2023 The American Association for the Advancement of Science. E) 4D Printing - Motion-controlled structures: Biodegradable hydrogel microrobotic swimmers with iron oxide magnetic nanoparticles for drug delivery. Reproduced under terms of CC-BY license.^[81] Copyright 2019 The Authors, published by American Chemical Society. F) 4D Printing - Shape and size adaptation to external stimuli: i) Microoctopus with dynamically tunable size and mechanical properties via covalent adaptable microstructures. Size variation over 0 h (left), 2 h (middle), and 4 h (right). Scale bar: 20 μm . Reproduced under terms of CC-BY license.^[82] Copyright 2023 The Authors, published by Wiley-VCH. ii) Capillary-force-driven self-assembly in various solvents (ethyl acetate (left), n-pentane (center), isopropyl alcohol (right)). Scale bar: 20 μm . Reproduced with permission.^[83] Copyright 2021 Wiley-VCH. iii) Two-in-one photoresist: degradable and non-degradable features based on the laser power during fabrication. Reproduced under terms of CC-BY license.^[84] Copyright 2023 The Authors, published by Wiley-VCH. G) Approaches for sub-100 nm high-resolution features: i) STED-based MPL for high-resolution 3D printing. Scale bar: 100 nm. Reproduced with permission.^[85] Copyright 2022 American Chemical Society. ii) and iii) Modulated cross-section of printed lines possess the ability to mimic the extraordinary structural color of the blue *Morpho* butterflies. Reproduced under Optica Publishing Group Open Access Publishing Agreement.^[86] Copyright 2019 The Authors, published by Optica Publishing Group. iv) High-resolution photonic crystal with lateral features of 60 nm achieved by radical quenching. Reproduced with permission.^[87] Copyright 2012 American Chemical Society. v) Isotropic feature size reduction using oxygen plasma etching. Buckyball before (left) and after (right) 5 etching cycles. Scale bar: 1 μm . Reproduced with permission.^[88] Copyright 2018 Elsevier.

structures with resolutions in the tens of micrometers by combining MPL with thermal debinding and sintering (Figure 3C). Concurrently, Bauer et al.^[96] presented a sinterless way to print silica glass using MPL-based 3D printing. These materials have a wide range of potential applications, including advanced optics and photonics, microfluidics, and biomedical fields. Conversely, Li et al.^[80] developed inks for 3D printing of various materials at nanoscale resolution, including inorganic substances like semiconductors, metal oxides, and metals, as well as their combinations (Figure 3D). This approach offers an alternative pathway for material processing in MPL-based printing, utilizing a photo-

chemical process that involves the bonding of colloidal nanocrystals. Another pathway for MPL-based printing involves multi-step absorption instead of multi-photon absorption. Based on dynamics in the triplet states, as demonstrated by ref. [97, 98], this process leads to self-deactivation of the photoinitiator, which positively impacts both the speed and efficiency of the printing process by altering the polymerization threshold.

Furthermore, active photosensitive materials have recently garnered significant attention. Using these materials, printed structures possess specific properties that respond to external stimuli, while this response refers to the ability to evolve over

time, for instance, by changing shape or size or triggering a function that can lead to motion, such as a magnetic response. Due to such capabilities, this field is often referred to as 4D printing and is rapidly emerging for the generation of microactuators, microsensors, microrobots, smart tissue engineering, and more, as recently highlighted in review articles by Mainik et al.^[99] and Jian et al.^[100] Responses to external stimuli can be achieved through materials incorporating additives like liquid crystals,^[101] shape memory fibers,^[102] iron nanoparticles (Figure 3E).^[81] Additionally, the use of alkoxyamine chemistry has enabled the creation of covalent adaptable microstructures with adjustable mechanical properties (Figure 3F, i). The change in the mechanical properties results from an increase in the structure's volume, which directly affects Young's modulus.^[82] Moreover, 4D printing can also be realized through fine features, enabling unique bidirectional and reversible self-assembly of microstructures (Figure 3F, ii). These can be driven by diverse wetting behaviors influenced by capillary forces.^[83] Another example of 4D printing, potentially applicable in smart tissue engineering or mechanics, involves the use of light-stabilized dynamic materials. These materials allow for tailoring the degradability and non-degradability within a single photoresist by varying the laser power in MPL-based printing^[84] (Figure 3F, iii), or they can degrade in the absence of light.^[103]

2.3. Advancements in Resolution

The minimum feature size determines the resolution in MPL-based printing, which is a critical property that significantly influences the functionality of the printed structures, especially those intended to manipulate electromagnetic radiation. Thanks to MPL's nonlinear nature, single features can attain sub-100 nm resolution.^[13] However, features of 3D printed structures often measure larger values, particularly when employing a layer-by-layer approach. The primary factor influencing the minimum achievable feature size in MPL is the voxel size, which is significantly affected by various factors. These include the laser parameters, the numerical aperture of the microscope objective, and the duration for which the photosensitive material is exposed to laser radiation.^[14,15] Additionally, the feature size is influenced by various technical aspects of MPL printer, the substrates used, and the properties of the photosensitive materials. Notably, the properties of these materials can have a significant and negative impact on the size of features due to inherent proximity and memory effects.^[104]

Therefore, the resolution in traditional MPL-based 3D printing is not infinitely small. Typically, the minimum feature size is limited to a width of 150 nm, while the minimum feature height is usually three times larger. This limitation is attributed to the inherent ellipsoidal shape of the voxel;^[14] however, it has been demonstrated that the aspect ratio of a line can be modified by altering the degree of nonlinearity used in inducing MPL.^[36]

Thus, although the resolution of traditional MPL printing processes is advanced, it has not yet consistently attained the level required to compete with the resolution of traditional lithographic methods. Nevertheless, as the utilization of MPL-based 3D printing in precision-demanding fields, such as optics and photonics, grows, efforts to enhance its resolution are becoming in-

creasingly vital. To this end, several strategies leveraging different strategies have been developed in recent years to surpass the resolution limits in traditional MPL, aiming to achieve sub-100 nm features.

One of the most notable advancements in enhancing MPL resolution involves the use of stimulated emission depletion (STED).^[104] This method employs shaped continuous wave laser radiation at a wavelength different from the printing laser, allowing for local inhibition of polymerization (Figure 3G, i). This inhibition is achieved either by altering the state of the initially excited molecule or by interacting with additional molecules in the photoresist. Through this approach, a minimum feature size of only 9 nm has been achieved in 2D printing.^[105] However, applying this technique for true 3D printing of arbitrary structures remains challenging. For instance, although 2D printing enabled achieving a resolution of 39 nm, the resolution of a 3D woodpile did not surpass the sub-100 nm regime.^[85] These challenges are primarily due to the complex optical setups needed to precisely align both laser wavelengths within the focal volume.

Another method to enhance MPL resolution utilizes highly reflective substrates, such as silicon,^[106] or a thin film of photosensitive material.^[107] This approach enables the modification of the cross-section of simple structures, such as cylinders or lines, within the sub-100 nm regime (Figure 3G, ii). The structural modification occurs due to an interference effect, which results from the formation of a standing wave within the photosensitive material.^[106] Although this approach is limited to 2D structures, it is particularly effective for applications requiring structural colors (Figure 3G, iii).^[26,34,86,108,109]

For advanced resolution in true 3D printing using MPL, chemical quenchers are highly effective. They reduce the polymerization threshold and radical diffusion properties of photoresists,^[110] mitigating proximity and memory effects. In this way, they enable the fabrication of complex 3D structures with minimum feature sizes of 60 nm (Figure 3G, iv).^[87] Conversely, recent trends utilizing post-processing solutions like oxygen plasma etching have demonstrated significant reductions in structural features (Figure 3G, v),^[55,88] achieving sizes as small as 55 nm while preserving 3D integrity.^[88] Additionally, methods such as pyrolysis or calcination are useful not only for the fabrication of purely inorganic structures but also for achieving structural shrinkage and thus high resolution features (Figure 3B).^[73,111] The maximum shrinkage rate can be up to 78% across the entire printed volume.^[112] Combining oxygen plasma etching with heat treatments like pyrolysis or calcination offers complementary advantages.^[88]

Furthermore, another interesting approach to enhancing the resolution of MPL was recently proposed by Lio et al.^[113] The authors introduced a glass substrate sputter-coated with an epsilon-near-zero (ENZ) metamaterial, consisting of a metal-insulator-metal-insulator (MIMI) structure. The substrate facilitated a reduction in voxel size through nonlinear light-matter interactions. This advancement allowed the authors to create 2D nanostructures with a feature height of 5 nm and a feature width of 200 nm using the photosensitive material IPL780 from Nanoscribe, achieving an 89% decrease in height and a 50% reduction in width compared to traditional MPL with the same process parameters.

2.4. Advancements in Throughput

While MPL has remarkably demonstrated its exceptional versatility as a 3D printing method, particularly in precisely functionalizing surfaces from several hundred micrometers to a few millimeters, it faces a significant limitation: the slow speed of serial printing. This drawback significantly hinders the wider adoption of MPL-based 3D printing in various research fields and in industry.

Given the high resolution achievable with a single voxel in building a 3D structure, serial MPL-based printing can be likened to using a fine pencil for drawing. Such precision allows for the creation of finely detailed features, but completing an entire artwork is extremely time-consuming. In MPL, the fabrication time, or process speed, is significantly influenced by the minimum size of the structural features and the overall size of the structure. These structural characteristics determine the required fineness of the slicing and hatching process of a structure, which, in turn, impacts the number of laser exposures needed for printing. Generally, a greater number of exposure events results in a longer fabrication time. Additionally, the limited field-of-view (FOV) of microscope objectives, especially for those with high numerical aperture required for high-resolution printing, significantly affects processing speed. This is because translation stages are required more frequently for large-area processing, interrupting the printing process, although, as previously mentioned, it is feasible to synchronize stages and scanners.^[37]

Nevertheless, the inherent serial nature of traditional MPL still presents significant challenges in scaling up throughput, particularly when translating microscale effects to macroscale applications. In response, considerable efforts have been devoted in recent years to overcoming this limitation, as thoroughly detailed in a recent review by Balena et al.^[45]

A promising approach to address these challenges is increasing the number of laser foci, facilitating parallel fabrication of periodic structures. Generating multiple foci can be achieved through a microlens array^[114] or diffractive optical elements (DOEs). Specifically, DOEs have only recently been employed to increase MPL printing speed, notably in the production of scaffolds for biological applications^[115] (Figure 4A), and in the fabrication of large 3D mechanical metamaterials.^[116] The use of DOEs has been further advanced with the integration of acousto-optical deflectors and a digital mask. In this method, known as acousto-optic scanning spatial-switching (Figure 4B), multiple foci can be individually controlled to create arbitrary 3D structures.^[100]

Furthermore, spatial light modulators (SLMs) offer an alternative method for generating multiple foci in MPL. Compared to diffractive optical elements (DOEs), SLMs provide more flexible beam shaping capabilities. They enable the creation of any number of multi-foci,^[119] allow for individual control of each focus,^[120] can shape the laser beam into single layers of 3D structures,^[121] and even make it possible to print an entire 3D structure through a single exposure.^[122] However, the use of SLMs in MPL remains challenging due to their low frame rates, which is critical for fast and precise 3D printing.

An alternative to SLMs and an emerging trend in the field of MPL is the use of Digital Mirror Devices (DMDs). DMDs consist of thousands of micromirrors that can deflect laser radiation into

desired patterns at higher frame rates. As a result, DMDs facilitate high-speed 3D printing using multi-foci (Figure 4C),^[117] and these foci can be individually controlled.^[123] Additionally, the use of DMDs can be combined with a micro-lens array to enhance throughput in 2D printing.^[124]

However, while parallel printing is primarily confined to the processing of periodic structures, the capabilities of DMDs extend far beyond merely generating multi-foci. Recent advancements in fs laser systems, particularly in the development of high-power fs lasers, allow DMDs to efficiently project fs laser radiation directly into a single layer of a 3D printed structure via spatiotemporal shaping of the laser radiation (Figure 4D). This method facilitates high throughput in MPL-based printing while preserving the resolution of traditional MPL approaches.^[31,32] Thus, DMD-based MPL currently offers one of the fastest throughputs without compromising the inherent versatility of MPL (Figure 4E). Additionally, a recent study has demonstrated the potential for photoinhibition in conjunction with DMD-based MPL printing, hinting at the imminent possibility of achieving printing features with resolutions below 100 nm.^[125]

3. Challenges and Perspectives

Despite recent advancements, MPL-based 3D printing continues to face challenges hindering its widespread dissemination and limiting its application in advanced AM of micro- and nanostructures. However, overcoming these challenges necessitates a collaborative effort combining expertise from both the natural sciences and engineering, essential for unlocking the full potential of MPL. Ideally, MPL-based 3D printing should enable to processing more intricate structures with higher resolution, either over larger areas or in bigger volumes, using a diverse portfolio of photosensitive materials, each tailored for specific applications.

Building upon this, one major challenge in MPL-based 3D printing remains the efficient scaling up of throughput. Although MPL has experienced significant enhancements in this area, with throughput improving by more than two orders of magnitude over the past five years, further optimization is necessary. Recent advancements enable now the processing of larger surfaces and volumes on several cm² and mm³ scale, respectively, within a reasonable time.^[31,45,116–118] However, additional optimization is particularly necessary when it comes to fabricating 3D structures with cm³ volume, especially when the structures comprise fine features with sub- μm features, as resolution significantly impacts printing time, adhering to the fifth power law, as per Tenant's law, originally established by ref. [126] and adjusted for MPL-based 3D printing by ref. [127].

Looking ahead, the use of DMDs in MPL-based 3D printing demonstrates substantial potential for further throughput optimization as DMDs enable the generation of multi-foci,^[117,123] as well as layer projection.^[31,32] Additionally, DMDs can be efficiently employed as digital masks in conjunction with static beam shaping solutions like DOEs.^[100] However, it is crucial to advance DMD technology by enhancing high-speed reconfiguration capabilities and increasing pixel counts. Such improvements would permit more precise control over laser exposure in both time and space, which is necessary to increase speed and resolution in MPL.

Figure 4. Advanced MPL-based 3D printing for enhanced throughput. A) Parallel 3D printing of periodic structures using a DOE. Reproduced under terms of CC-BY license.^[115] Copyright 2020 The Authors, published by Nature Publishing Group. B) Multi-foci generation through a DMD and associated printed structures. A maximum number of 2000 foci was achieved. The minimum printing time for each unit cell was 150 ms. Reproduced under terms of CC-BY license.^[117] Copyright 2023 The Authors, published by Nature Publishing Group. C) Advancement in MPL through acousto-optic scanning and spatial-switching. The highlighted 3D structure was produced in approximately 55 ms. Reproduced under terms of CC-BY license.^[118] Copyright 2023 The Authors, published by IOP. D) Schematic illustration of layer-projection MPL based on spatiotemporal beam shaping using a DMD. The resulting printed structure was fabricated in less than 250 ms. The Reproduced under terms of CC-BY license.^[32] Copyright 2021 The Authors, published by Nature Publishing Group. E) Results of printing complex 3D structures via layer-projection MPL. Reproduced with permission.^[31] Copyright 2019 The American Association for the Advancement of Science.

Nevertheless, effective throughput optimization in MPL remains a challenging task, regardless of the devices employed to enhance MPL speed. Generally, it has been suggested that throughput in 3D printing using light can be estimated by the number of specific voxels required for printing a particular volume.^[116] This method offers a valuable preliminary benchmark for comparing various MPL upscaling solutions and their performance against other 3D printing methods. However, the evaluation of throughput in MPL-based 3D printing is more complex than it initially appears. Voxel dimensions are influenced by a myriad of factors, including the specifications of the MPL printing device, the microscope objective, the complexity and overall dimensions of the structure, and the properties of the photosensitive material, among others. It is important to note that structural characteristics can vary significantly across different applications, leading to considerable variations in the optimal voxel size for rapid MPL-based printing. This variation can be evident even within a single structure comprising features of varying dimen-

sions, while most published printing parameters to date have been more specifically tailored for individual structures rather than being optimized for general use.

A potential solution to address the complexities of rapid MPL-based printing could involve integrating grayscale control,^[46,48] further enhanced by machine learning.^[128] This approach, particularly when utilizing DMDs, as indicated by ref. [32], would allow for precise modulation of voxel dimensions at any given volumetric position, thereby optimizing the number of printing events independently of the structural design while simultaneously maximizing throughput and maintaining the highest printing quality.

Specifically, the integration of machine learning into grayscale-based MPL could greatly simplify the process of identifying optimal printing parameters for novel photosensitive materials. This advancement is increasingly relevant, considering the recent trend in revising the chemistry of photosensitive materials for 3D printing. The progress in this area has led to a diverse

range of new materials, encompassing organic (both synthetic and natural), inorganic, and hybrid compositions.^[23,63] Moreover, these materials can also be functional or capable of undergoing structural changes in response to external stimuli,^[99] and each category could potentially benefit from different post-processing methods. In this context, pyrolysis/calcination emerges as an attractive option,^[73] as it effectively enhances the refractive index^[129] and optical damage threshold of structures,^[130] benefits that are highly advantageous for micro-optics.

In the realm of photosensitive materials, ongoing challenges persist in optimizing these materials for more efficient processing. For instance, developing high-efficiency radical quenchers and photoinitiators could significantly enhance the throughput and resolution of structures, potentially achieving feature sizes below 100 nm.

From an application perspective, the development of photosensitive materials with a high refractive index exceeding 1.9 or active components is particularly promising in optics and photonics.^[131–133] Conversely, materials with a lower refractive index, around 1.3, may be more suitable for biomedical applications,^[134] aiding in the efficient study of cellular interactions with scaffolds and providing valuable insights into cell studies and tissue engineering.

Another significant challenge in MPL-based 3D printing is enhancing the optical performance of printed structures, as they often exhibit a slight yellow and fluorescent coloration, which is particularly disadvantageous for imaging applications. This issue mainly stems from the properties of photoinitiators. A promising solution to these challenges is to explore the processing of photosensitive materials without the use of photoinitiators, as highlighted by ref. [135]. Advancing in this direction could lead to the development of innovative organic, inorganic, or hybrid materials. It may also further promote efficient printing of natural or bio-based materials on a small scale, as indicated by [136]. Moreover, this approach would allow for a deeper understanding of the interactions between ultrashort pulsed lasers and photosensitive materials. By conducting a thorough investigation of their physico-chemical properties, we can develop crucial theoretical models and design materials that are specifically tailored to meet the requirements of various applications.

Ultimately, addressing a majority of the described challenges could significantly impact the broader dissemination of MPL and lead to substantial improvements in the technique. However, the challenges in MPL extend beyond the aforementioned ones. Another major factor hindering the widespread adoption of MPL is the cost of MPL systems. The cost, largely driven by the price of the laser system, can rapidly exceed several hundred thousand euros, making MPL financially prohibitive for many potential users. In contrast, the use of monolithic diodes^[34] or microchips emitting ultrashort pulsed laser radiation^[35] could offer a viable solution to significantly reduce these costs. Simultaneously, their application could lead to the development of more compact MPL systems, thereby enhancing MPL's accessibility and practicality. However, it is noteworthy that, to date, these laser sources do not provide the necessary intensity for high-throughput MPL.

Therefore, to further tackle cost concerns and other challenges, revisiting and revising traditional MPL methods, similar to advancements in materials, may be a beneficial future perspective. While ultrafast pulsed lasers remain the preferred choice in laser-

based 3D printing, the potential of incoherent and low-intensity LED sources or compact laser diodes for achieving submicron resolution in 3D printing within a photoresin is noteworthy. Techniques such as triplet–triplet annihilation,^[137] triplet fusion upconversion nanocapsules,^[138] and two-step absorption^[139,140] could yield results akin to MPL due to their nature of enabling spatially confined excitation near the focal point of the light.

Another innovative approach involves utilizing resonance energy transfer in a donor–acceptor pair for true 3D printing. This method suggests the use of sequential multi-photon processes as opposed to simultaneous ones. Thus, it offers to employ low-power, cost-effective, continuous-wave lasers for initiating chemical reactions in photosensitive materials within the focal volume.^[141]

4. Summary and Future Opportunities

To summarize, this perspective article has showcased significant advancements and trends in MPL. Recent advancements have positioned MPL as a superior technique in 3D printing, particularly for AM of micro- and nanostructures. The existing challenges, requiring further advancements through a collaborative effort from interdisciplinary fields to fully harness MPL's capabilities, should not be viewed as indicators of inefficiency. Instead, they underscore the considerable potential of this laser-based printing method for the future.

Over the past years, interest in MPL has risen markedly, particularly in research contexts. It is anticipated that the peak of this interest has not yet been reached, considering MPL's unique 3D printing capabilities, which are highly advantageous for numerous applications. Intriguingly, the versatility of MPL has expanded significantly in recent years. Currently, MPL's scope extends beyond merely printing arbitrary 3D structures from hybrid photoresists; it also encompasses the printing of various materials, including multi-materials.^[80,142] This broadening of MPL's capabilities has notably enhanced its practicality, offering the prospect of efficiently manufacturing real-world applications in the near future, particularly on challenging surfaces such as the end-face of an optical fiber.

Looking toward the distant future, further optimization of MPL-based printing requires careful consideration. Transitioning MPL-based 3D printing to industrial use, particularly for large-area production in applications like roll-to-roll processes or wafer surface processing, involves more than just scaling up MPL throughput. This necessitates integrating MPL with other manufacturing methods, leveraging MPL's great adaptability. For instance, MPL could be combined with other 3D printing methods that rely on one-photon absorption. Moreover, MPL-based 3D printing could benefit from advancements aimed at making the process smarter, with a particular emphasis on advanced metrology. This might be crucial for in-line, high-resolution monitoring of 3D micro- and nanostructures during printing. Real-time characterization of the structures' geometry and material properties could pave the way for integrating machine learning and artificial intelligence. This integration could be further augmented with inverse design strategies, thereby providing full access to exceptional precision in spatial arrangement and degree of modification. However, all these efforts demand a multidisciplinary approach, combining expertise from various fields of engineering.

Regardless of how the future unfolds, MPL's unique versatility and adaptability, whether used alone or in combination with other manufacturing techniques, hold enormous potential for advanced engineering in fields such as microfluidics, biomedicine, microrobotics, photonics, optics, electronics, micromechanics, biomimetics, and more. Thanks to advancements in machine learning and novel computer-aided design strategies, recent developments in computer science are set to further enhance the efficiency of printing complex 3D structures at the micro- and nanoscale. In conclusion, the promising prospects of MPL-based printing may pave the way for exploring novel applications in life sciences, healthcare, quantum computing, and energy harvesting – all critically important fields in our world today.

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Conflict of Interest

The authors declare no conflict of interest.

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